

Machine Unlearning through confusion

Sourav Ganguly

Email: 211011002@iitdh.ac.in

Abstract

Machine learning techniques excel at uncovering hidden patterns and intricate details with minimal human effort. However, data collection and labeling are often done manually, which can introduce errors. To train an ML model, a large number of data points are required, and manual tagging can lead to incorrect class labels. These inaccuracies can subtly affect the model's accuracy. In the modern era, where vast amounts of data are available, training an ML model can take significant time, ranging from a few hours to several days. When a model has already been trained on corrupted data, identifying and removing faulty subsets becomes exceedingly difficult. Any erroneous data can corrupt the model's learning, and retraining the model after removing corrupted data points is time-consuming and resource-intensive. In this study, we aim to perform Machine Unlearning to remove wrongly learned concepts from the model, making it more efficient without needing retraining. We investigate the effects of Machine Unlearning and propose an efficient technique for implementing it on classification datasets. Our work assumes that the model has been fully trained with the complete dataset and later realizes that some data points are corrupted and need to be unlearned to improve the model's performance.

Keywords - Classification model, Machine Unlearning, Machine Unlearning through Confusion

1 Introduction

Since the advent of computers, humans have achieved many remarkable milestones that were considered dreams centuries ago. Computers not only perform complex mathematical calculations but also uncover patterns in data. According to Antonio Neri, president of Hewlett Packard Enterprise, **Data is the new currency**. With the exponential growth of data, effective methods for understanding, managing, and extracting meaningful insights from it have become essential. To address these needs, data science [1, 2] and machine learn-

ing [3, 4] have been utilized. Various sectors, including finance [5, 6, 7], healthcare [8, 9, 10], and administration [11, 12, 13], have benefited significantly from these technologies. Machine learning, commonly abbreviated as ML, is a widely used technique that enables machines to perform laborious tasks quickly and efficiently.

Although a trained ML model can be very effective in the long run, the training process is expensive in terms of both time and resources. Training on large datasets, such as those in medicine or natural language processing [14, 15], can take from several hours to several days. If, after completing the training, it is discovered that the dataset contains some corrupted or incorrect data points, removing these points and retraining the model becomes very challenging. This leads to a significant waste of time and resources. To avoid the need for retraining, Machine Unlearning (MuL) [16, 17] is used. Machine Unlearning can be informally defined as a technique that allows the system to forget data points that provide incorrect information. MuL is an important concept with the potential to significantly aid in managing complex models with data discrepancies. In the following subsections, we highlight some of the existing literature on this topic and explain the motivation behind our work.

1.1 Literature Review

The concept of unlearning in machine learning is relatively new, but its importance in big industries has led to substantial research. [17] propose the SISA technique, which slices datasets into multiple sets, each trained by a weak learner. When a data point needs to be forgotten, only the relevant set is retrained, limiting the need to retrain the entire model. However, this method’s random division of data points can lead to complications when multiple deletion requests are made, as it requires updating all learning models.

[18] introduce a formal framework for verifying data deletion requests in machine learning as a service (MLaaS), with a novel backdoor-based mechanism that ensures high confidence in certifying data deletion with minimal impact on the accuracy of the ML service. This framework is implemented in the Athena [18, 19] model.

[20] taxonomize approximate unlearning approaches and metrics, identifying verification error as a key metric. They propose a new training objective to minimize this error, validated through empirical evaluation on CIFAR-10, CIFAR-100, and IMDB sentiment analysis. [21] propose the DeltaGrad algorithm, which uses cached information from the training phase for rapid retraining, supported by both theoretical and empirical evidence of its effectiveness. [22] introduce a new approximate deletion method for linear and logistic models with a computational cost linear in the feature dimension and independent of the number of training samples, significantly outperforming existing methods.

1.2 Motivation behind the work

Most of the existing literature focuses on removing data points from the dataset either before training begins or while training is ongoing. In this work, we address the scenario where an ML model has already been trained. An apt analogy for this situation is a student who has memorized something incorrectly and later realizes the mistake, necessitating the unlearning of the incorrect concept. To the best of our knowledge, this paper is among the first to tackle the problem of Machine Unlearning (MuL) after a model has been trained. The primary objective is to find a solution for situations where retraining the model is costly due to substantial training time. The model discussed in this paper offers a straightforward solution that incurs only a minimal (nearly negligible) loss in accuracy.

Our primary contributions are outlined below:

- We introduce a novel method for performing Machine Unlearning on a model that has already been trained on a corrupted dataset.
- Conducting extensive testing of our technique on various ML models.

2 Background

In this section, we shall highlight the different notations used throughout the paper along with specific information regarding the various key components of the main idea highlighted in this paper.

2.1 Machine Learning

Machine learning [3] is a subset of artificial intelligence (AI) that focuses on developing algorithms enabling computers to learn from data and improve performance on tasks without explicit programming. It involves creating models that identify patterns and make predictions or decisions based on input data. Machine learning algorithms can be broadly categorized into three types: supervised learning [23], unsupervised learning [24], and reinforcement learning [25]. Supervised learning involves training a model on labeled data, allowing the algorithm to map inputs to corresponding outputs. Unsupervised learning involves training a model on unlabeled data, where the algorithm identifies patterns or structures in the data without explicit guidance. Reinforcement learning involves training a model to make sequential decisions by interacting with an environment and receiving feedback in the form of rewards or penalties [26]. In this paper, we primarily focus on classification tasks [27] and will thus concentrate on certain well-known classification algorithms.

2.2 Common Notations

This paper evaluates the effectiveness of the technique discussed in the upcoming sections against a large number of classification models. To facilitate

understanding, we introduce the important notations utilized throughout the paper.

Let the input feature vector be denoted as $x \in \mathcal{X}$ and the output vector as y . We approximate a function $f : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow y$. Since the function is a surrogate, the output values may not be identical to the original output vector, i.e., $f(x) = \hat{y} \forall x \in \mathcal{X}$. As this paper primarily deals with classification problems, $y \in \mathbb{Z}$.

The dataset $\mathcal{X}$ is composed of two parts: $X_{abs} \cup \hat{X}$, where $\hat{X}$ denotes the subset of faulty data points and X_{abs} denotes the set formed by removing the faulty data points from the original dataset.

In our experiments, we utilize neural networks [28]. We denote the weight matrix¹ associated with the $(l - 1)$ th layer to the l th layer as $W^l \prod_{l=1}^{L-1}$, and the weight value for the connection from the i th neuron in the $(l - 1)$ th layer to the j th neuron in the l th layer as W_{ij}^l . The activation function at each step is represented by $\phi(\cdot) : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$.

The loss function used in most of the algorithms is categorical cross-entropy. The formula for categorical cross-entropy is provided in the following equation (1)

$$L(y, \hat{y}) = - \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}} y_c \cdot \log(\hat{y}_c) \quad (1)$$

2.3 Classification models

Classification models are machine learning algorithms designed to categorize data points into predefined classes or labels. These models are extensively utilized across various applications, including spam detection [29], medical diagnosis [30], and image recognition [31], to accurately predict the category of new data points. Some of the standard Classification models that are also utilized in this paper are as follows

2.3.1 Support Vector Machine

Support Vector Machines (SVMs) [32] are a powerful and versatile class of supervised learning models used for classification and regression tasks. They work by finding the optimal hyperplane that best separates the data into different classes, maximizing the margin between the classes. SVMs are particularly effective in high-dimensional spaces and are robust to overfitting, especially in cases where the number of dimensions exceeds the number of samples. They are widely applied in fields such as image recognition, text categorization, and bioinformatics due to their accuracy and ability to handle complex, non-linear data through kernel functions.

¹To understand the working of Neural Networks in a better way and understand the notation further you can follow [28]

2.3.2 Decision Trees

A Decision Tree Classifier [33] is a simple yet powerful machine learning algorithm used for classification tasks. It works by recursively splitting the dataset into subsets based on the feature that results in the most significant information gain or the greatest reduction in impurity. Each internal node of the tree represents a decision based on a feature, each branch represents the outcome of the decision, and each leaf node represents a class label. Decision Trees are easy to interpret and visualize, making them useful for understanding and diagnosing model predictions. They are widely used in various fields, including finance, healthcare, and marketing, for their ability to handle both categorical and numerical data.

2.3.3 Neural Networks

Neural Networks [28] are a class of machine learning models inspired by the structure and function of the human brain. They consist of interconnected layers of nodes (neurons), where each node processes input data and passes the output to the next layer. Neural Networks are capable of learning complex patterns and representations through a process called training, which involves adjusting the weights of the connections between nodes based on the error of the predictions. They are highly effective for tasks such as image and speech recognition, natural language processing, and game playing, thanks to their ability to model non-linear relationships and handle large-scale data.

2.4 A brief insight about how humans perform unlearning

In this section, we aim to explore various methods humans use to unlearn, which will inform the development of an efficient unlearning technique in subsequent sections.

In everyday life, humans memorize a large number of things such as roads, landmarks, speeches, formulas, and equations. Repeated mental rehearsal is a highly effective method for memorization while forgetting occurs naturally when we cease to actively recall information. New experiences continually shape our lives, gradually supplanting memories we wish to forget with fresh ones, leading to their eventual disappearance from our recollection.

Machines, however, lack this intuitive process due to their vast storage capacity. In the realm of Machine Learning, the challenge is compounded by the machine's ability to uncover subtle patterns that may escape human observation. Consequently, isolating specific data points and mitigating their influence becomes a daunting task.

As previously mentioned, the method of reinforcing memory through repetition is not easily translatable to machines. Expanding on human unlearning techniques, we note that inducing confusion can effectively aid in forgetting. For instance, consider a scenario where a child is shown an image of a cat and is told it depicts a cat. The child associates the shape with a cat. However, if

the same image is associated with other animals like dogs, goats, and tigers, it creates confusion, leading the child’s brain to disregard the original association. This concept forms the basis of our Theorem 1. Building upon this theorem, we formulate our approach to perform machine unlearning.

To the best of our knowledge, this paper represents the first attempt to introduce machine unlearning through the mechanism of confusion.

3 Proposed Approach

In this section, we discuss our approach to dealing with the Machine Learning problem. Unlearning some information is generally required when the learned information is incorrect or ambiguous ². We approach the problem of unlearning by formulating several cases.

- When the corrupted data points are known and their true classes are known before model training has started
- When the corrupted data points are known before the model training has started but their true classes are not known
- When the corrupted data points are known after the model has been trained but the true classes are unknown.
- When the corrupted data points are known after the model has been trained but the true classes are known.

On carefully observing the above cases, it is very clear that the first two cases are of very little interest to us. This is because we get to know before training the faulty data points and hence, we can suitably adjust our dataset such that the dataset that is used for training the model is free from any ambiguity. In the first case, not only we know the incorrect data points but also the correct labels corresponding to those data points. Thus, it would be logical to correct the class labels for those data points and then train the ML model.

In the second case, we can simply remove the faulty data points ($\hat{X}$) from the dataset and then use the remaining dataset(X_{abs}) to train our ML model. The remaining two cases are the major focus of this paper.

3.1 Machine Unlearning through confusion

We first shift our attention to the third case. We have $\hat{X}$ which is the faulty subset. Each element in $\hat{X}$ that is $\hat{x} \in \hat{X}$ has a corresponding label associated with it. For our convenience let us denote the class labels as $\hat{y}$ such that $\hat{y}_i = f(\hat{x}_i) \forall_{i \in \hat{X}}$. In an ideal situation, $(\hat{x}_i, \hat{y}_i) \forall_{i \in \hat{X}}$ should be absent from the training

²A very simple solution would be to follow when the number of samples to be deleted is small is the Ostrich algorithm [34] where we ignore the error introduced by incorrect samples. But this is not correct as it might lead to incorrect learning.

dataset. Thus, in this situation for each data point x_i can be associated with all the class labels $\mathcal{C}$ with equal probability. In other words all classes are equally probable for a data point $\hat{x}_i$. (For further understanding follow Theorem 1)

Keeping the above discussion in mind, we introduce our algorithm (Algorithm ??). We are given $X, \hat{X}, y$ and $\hat{y}$. Observe that we already have a trained model $f : X \rightarrow y$. Hence, the model is already trained on the faulty data points. We create a new dataset $(X_f, y_f) = \forall_{i \in \hat{X}} \forall_{j \in \mathcal{C} - \hat{y}_i} (\hat{x}_i, \hat{y}_j)$. In simpler words, we replicate all the faulty data points mapping against each of the classes once except for the class that $\hat{x}_i$ was originally mapped to. Thus, we introduce confusion to the model and also take care that each of the output classes of each faulty example is equi-probable. As soon as our refined dataset (X_f, y_f) is ready, we continue training our model f (which has already learned on the faulty examples) with the already learned weights as initial values upon the refined dataset (keeping all training conditions same). In this way, we ensure that the model has learned each faulty data point against all the classes which indirectly instructs the model to map each data point with equal probability to all the classes present in the dataset. The algorithm is given in algorithm 1

Theorem 1: *A data item whose label is a discrete uniform random variable and each possible label is mapped against a single data point, is similar to be an unknown sample or never learnt sample*

Proof: Let us consider a sample $\hat{x}_i \in \mathcal{X}$ is trained against a given output $\hat{y}_i$. If we know before training the ML, model that $\hat{x}_i$ is faulty i.e. the true label is unknown to us, we would remove $\hat{x}_i$ from $\mathcal{X}$. Thus, the filtered dataset is $X_{abs} = \mathcal{X} - \hat{X}$. We train our model on X_{abs} . Thus, for the model $\hat{x}_i \in \hat{X}$ is equally likely to belong in each of the category but it is impossible to know which class it actually belongs to. Thus, this induces confusion which is approximately similar to not knowing exactly the true label.

Algorithm 1 Machine un-learning through confusion (MuLtC)

- 1: **Input:** $X, \hat{X}, y, \hat{y}, h, \mathcal{C}$
 - 2: **Initialize:** h with already learnt weights upon training Machine Learning classification model h with inputs (X, y) , Empty list X_f
 - 3: **for** $i = 1$ to $length(\hat{X})$ **do**
 - 4: **for** $j \in \mathcal{C}$ **do**
 - 5: **if** $j \neq \hat{y}_i$ **then** Append $(\hat{x}_i, j)$ to X_f
 - 6: **end if**
 - 7: **end for**
 - 8: **end for**
 - 9: **Train_model** (h, X_f)
 - 10: (Note the train model function is used to further train the machine model used, the model is initialized with originally learnt weights h and is further trained using X_f)
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Ok now that the third case has been addressed, we can address the fourth

case by extrapolating the results of the third case. First, the model is trained using the complete dataset $\mathcal{X}$. After obtaining the model h , utilize Algorithm 1 to perform un-learning of the faulty data to obtain h_1 . Finally train the new refined model h_1 with the correct labels of the faulty data-points to obtain h_2 . However, in this paper, we restrict ourselves towards the discussion of the third case only.

4 Results

In this section, we discuss the results obtained on testing our method on some standard ML datasets. Keeping in mind that our algorithm is fit for classification-type datasets only, we briefly discuss the datasets utilized³.

4.1 Datasets Employed for the Evaluation of Our Algorithm

4.1.1 Pima diabetes dataset

The Pima Diabetes dataset is used to predict the onset of diabetes in patients based on several medical measurements. It comprises 768 samples, each with eight features: the number of pregnancies, glucose level, blood pressure, skin thickness, insulin level, BMI, diabetes pedigree function, and age. This dataset is a binary classification problem with two classes: diabetic (positive) and non-diabetic (negative), indicating whether a patient has diabetes. It is widely utilized for binary classification tasks in machine learning.

4.1.2 Iris dataset

As the Pima dataset is a binary class classification dataset, we are interested in making our algorithm complete to work with all types of classification problems. Thus, we move to the Iris dataset which is a multi-class classification. The Iris dataset is a classic machine learning and statistics dataset, often used for testing algorithms. It consists of 150 samples from three species of Iris flowers: setosa, versicolor, and virginica. Each sample includes four features: sepal length, sepal width, petal length, and petal width, measured in centimeters. The goal is to classify the samples into the correct species based on these features. This dataset is well-suited for classification tasks and is frequently used to demonstrate and benchmark machine learning algorithms.

4.1.3 MNIST dataset

The MNIST dataset is widely used in machine learning for handwritten digit recognition. It consists of 70,000 grayscale images of handwritten digits (0-9), each image being 28x28 pixels in size. The dataset is divided into 60,000 training

³The complete code and the relevant datasets can be found at https://github.com/Sourav1429/Machine_Unlearning.git

images and 10,000 test images. The goal is to classify each image into one of the ten-digit classes. This dataset is popular for benchmarking image processing and classification algorithms.

4.2 Results obtained and Analysis of the results obtained

The algorithm was applied to the given datasets in two different settings as given below

- Randomly choosing a set of data points and employing the MuLtC algorithm to unlearn those data points
- Randomly choosing a set of data points and changing their original labels, in order to make them corrupted data. Then, finally employing MuLtC to unlearn these data-points

We shall discuss both settings separately in the upcoming subsections. However, it is important to first discuss what our experiments try to convey. We try creating three independent models and compare the accuracies. We further check whether the randomly chosen data points to be unlearned are producing different results or not. The three models are given below

- **Original model:** This, model trains itself on the complete dataset (including the non-targeted data points and the targeted data points). Let denote this model as h_{or}
- **Retraining model:** In this model, we purify our dataset by removing all the targeted data points and then train our ML model. Let us denote this model as h_r .
- **Additional training model:** This model employs the MuLtC algorithm to create a separate subset $S_a = (\hat{X}, y_a)$ such that $(y_a)_i = \mathcal{C} - \hat{y}_i \forall_{i=1}^{|\hat{X}|}$ of the targeted data points. We now utilize the saved weights and bias from h_{or} as the initial parameters and then further train on the data subset S_a . Let us denote this model as h_a .

4.2.1 Random Unlearning of Targeted Data Points

In this setting, we randomly choose a few data points. Our aim in this setting is to make the model unlearn the targeted data point. This is one of the most challenging setting. The reason being the decision boundaries of a classification type ML problem is not set by one or two data points but a set of data points decide upon the decision boundary. Hence, randomly selecting a few data points and unlearning them does not affect much. However, we trained our models h_{or} , h_f and h_a and the accuracy comparison is as given in table 1 and 2

To finally check the effectiveness of our model, we take one sample from the targeted list and predict its label. Some relevant test points can be found in figures 1, 2 and 3

Dataset used	h_{or} acc.	h_f acc.	h_a acc.
PIMA	0.68	0.662	0.659
IRIS	0.97	0.967	0.967
MNIST	0.989	0.988	0.985

Table 1: Accuracy comparison for SVM

Figure 1: MNIST data point unlearnt and predicted as 0

4.2.2 Random Modification of Targeted Data-points Followed by Unlearning

In the second setting, we select a set of target data points and change their label abruptly. As a result upon training the accuracies are not good. Finally upon performing unlearning of the corrupted data points the accuracy seemed to increase. Thus, imparting better and improved learning. This is a more practical case where MuL should be used. The previous setting acts as the control experiment. In these experiments we use Neural networks (NNs) to test the effectiveness of MuLc over NNs. The comparisons are shown in table 3

4.3 Analysis of the results obtained

We observe that in the first setting, there is not much fluctuation between the three models. In the IRIS dataset, the models almost do not change at all. The reason for this behavior is that a model learns its boundaries from a large number of data points. Hence, if one or two behaves as an outlier, it does not affect the others and hence, the boundaries do not change much. However, when a large number of points are required to be unlearnt such as one complete class has been misclassified and already trained, in those cases, this technique is very effective as is evident by our second setting.

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Selected testing set [118. 84. 0.551] True label: 1
[0]

Selected testing set [125. 70. 0.205] True label: 1
[0]

Selected testing set [132. 80. 0.186] True label: 0
[0]

Selected testing set [168. 74. 0.537] True label: 1
[1]

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Figure 2: Some predictions (targeted data points) of PIMA dataset

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Selected testing set [5.7 2.6 3.5 1. ] True label: 1
Predicted label: [1]
Selected testing set [5. 3.5 1.3 0.3] True label: 0
Predicted label: [0]
Selected testing set [5. 3.5 1.3 0.3] True label: 0
Predicted label: [0]
Selected testing set [6.1 2.6 5.6 1.4] True label: 2
Predicted label: [2]

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Figure 3: Some predictions (targeted data points) of IRIS dataset

The tables 1, 2, 3 summarize the performance of the three models we aim to study in this paper. From the tables, we can conclude that the PIMA dataset’s performance is best in the case of the Decision Tree classifier. One of the major causes for this behavior can be that SVM with RBF kernel or the neural network is overfitting and so the accuracy is fairly low.

The figures give some insight as how the model is performing. One big observation that we can make from our MuLtC model is that although it might not completely forget the data points as that of Retraining model, it does not change the perception for non-targeted data. That is it does not alter results for the non-targeted data with respect to the Original model. However, this behaviour was partially observed while training SVM using MNIST data. The purpose of Unlearning should be correcting our mistakes and not making new mistakes. MuLtC has bypassed those problems as it does not remove any data point from the dataset but adds more data thus, wrong beliefs being limited does not affect the decision boundaries much.

Dataset used	h_{or} acc.	h_f acc.	h_a acc.
PIMA	1.0	0.997	0.992
IRIS	1.0	0.99	1.0
MNIST	1.0	0.996	0.978

Table 2: Accuracy comparison for Decision Tree Classifier

Figure 4: MNIST data point unlearned

Dataset used	h_{or} acc.	h_f acc.	h_a acc.
PIMA	0.651	0.677	0.682
IRIS	0.95	0.985	0.982
MNIST	0.914	0.942	0.938

Table 3: Accuracy comparison for Neural Networks

5 Conclusion and Future work

In this study, we thoroughly studied the problem of Machine Unlearning and its need in practical life problems. We further analysed upon how human beings can unlearn something which was already learned through confusion. Using this metaphor, we constructed technique, to perform unlearning of faulty classification data points after an ML model has already been trained over the complete dataset. We further verified our postulates on some standard ML datasets.

In the future works, it would be interesting to address the problem of Machine Unlearning for Regression type problems and also finding more robust ways of performing unlearning when true labels of the faulty points are known to us but after the model has already been trained over incorrect dataset. Finding more robust techniques to perform unlearning on time series data can also be an interesting research direction.

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